

Fatty Acid Composition of Some Minor Oils

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The oilseeds selected for the present work were *Bombax malabaricum* (Savar), *Buchanania lanzan* (Charoli), *Mesua ferrea* (Nahor), *Michelia champaca* (Champha), *Terminalia catappa*, (Jangli badam), *Thespesia populnea* (Bhendi), and *Xanthium strumarium* (Gokhru).

Moisture and oil content of the seed kernels were determined. The oils, obtained by solvent extraction from the seed kernels were analysed for their physical and chemical characteristics. The methyl esters of the oils (freed from unsaponifiable matter) were analysed for their fatty acid composition by gas liquid chromatography.

The major fatty acid components of all the oils were found to be palmitic, oleic and linoleic acids. Palmitic acid was found to be between 33.8% and 38.7% except in the case of *Mesua ferrea* (palmitic 16.3%) and *Xanthium strumarium* (palmitic 8.3%). All the oils had more than 55 per cent of total unsaturated acids except *Buchanania lanzan* (46%). Stearic acid was found to be minor fatty acid in all the oils and varied between 3.1 and 13.5 per cent. *Mesua ferrea* was found to be rich in oleic acid (59.9%) and *Xanthium strumarium* was found to be rich in linoleic acid content (69.2%). The fatty acid composition of the oils are compared with the values reported by earlier workers.

INDIA produces a large number of minor oilseeds which can provide more than three lakh tons of vegetable oils and fats per year. So far, a few of them have been partly industrially exploited. However, a large number of these oilseeds which occur in forest and non forest areas in the country await systematic investigation. Literature indicates that these minor oils can be put to various uses such as soap making or for preparing fatty acids which have great industrial applications. For proper and economic utilization of these oils, information on general characteristics and fatty acid composition is of utmost importance.

Attempts have been made in the present investigation to study a few minor oilseeds. Although earlier workers have attempted to study the fatty acid composition of these oils, to some extent, by low temperature crystallization, ester fractionation, lead salt methods, reversed phase partition column chromatography etc., in the present investigation fatty acid composition has been studied by recent analytical technique viz., gas liquid chromatography.

The following oilseeds were selected for the present study:—*Bombax malabaricum* (Savar), a tall deciduous tree with straight buttersilk trunk and wide spreading branches is available throughout the hotter parts of India, Ceylon and Malaya. The cotton obtained from the capsules is extensively used for filling beds, cushions, and pillows¹. Thus, the seeds embedded in the cotton are a byproduct of this cotton industry. The characteristics and the fatty acid composition of the oil obtained from the seeds were first studied by Japanese workers Kinzo Kafuku *et al.*² as early as 1933. Venkata Rao *et al.*³ also studied the oil in 1943. The methods adopted by these workers were fractional crystallization,

Buchanania lanzan (Charoli): A medium sized tree, is found in dry deciduous forests throughout India and Burma, in North Western India from Sulez to Nepal⁴. The kernels are eaten raw or roasted and form a substitute for almond and are used in the manufacture of sweetmeats⁴. The seed kernels contain more than 50% of light yellow oil having mild pleasant aroma. The only report available on the study of this oil is by Godbole *et al.*⁵ who studied the characteristics of the oil and the fatty acid composition by fractional distillation in 1941.

Mesua ferrea (Nahor): A medium sized evergreen tree which is cultivated in gardens for its flowers. The tree is widely distributed in India and Ceylon⁶. The fatty acid composition of the oil has been studied by some earlier workers⁷⁻¹⁰ by ester fractionation methods. Recently Sreenivasan¹¹ and Badami *et al.*¹² have investigated this oil by GLC and reversed phase partition column chromatography respectively. The results obtained in the present study have been compared with those of these workers.

Michelia champaca (Champha): The tree is cultivated throughout India, in gardens for its fragrant flowers. The flowers yield a valuable essential oil used in perfumery. The trees also occur widely in the E. Sub-Himalayan tract and lower hills, Assam, Burma, W. Ghats and S. India⁶. In 1903 the oil was studied by Sack¹³ who reported the fatty acid composition as palmitic 30% and oleic 70%. After that only recently (1970) Bedi *et al.*¹⁴ have studied this oil by GLC. The results are presented in Table 2 and compared with those obtained in the present investigation.

Terminalia catappa (Jangli Badam): is a large deciduous tree indigenous to the beach forests of the Andaman Islands and cultivated in most parts of India and Burma, especially near the coast¹⁵. Recently, the Government of Maharashtra has undertaken the cultivation of these trees. The seed kernels taste somewhat like almonds and the oil can be a useful substitute for the oil of almond¹⁶.

The oil from the kernels of *T. catappa* occurring in Puerto Rico¹⁷, Formosa¹⁸, Phillipine¹⁹ and W. Africa²⁰ has been examined. Beri *et al.*¹⁶ have studied the fatty acid composition by bromination and fractional distillation. However, no report on the GLC analysis of the oil is available.

Thespesia populnea (Bhendi): This is a small tree available in the coastal forests of India and Burma and largely grown as a roadside tree in tropical regions²¹. The only report on the study of the oil from the seed kernel is that by Subbaram²² who studied the characteristics of the oil and its fatty acid composition by low temperature crystallization followed by fractional distillation.

Xanthium strumarium (Gokhu): This is a common weed in hotter parts of India. The yield per acre of this oil bearing seed is high, 500-600 lbs²³. The seed is enclosed in a thorny cover which is hard and tenacious and is difficult to remove by mechanical means.

The general characteristics and the fatty acid composition of the oil obtained from the kernels has been studied by few workers^{24,25,26}. The latest available report is that by Badami *et al.*¹² who used reversed phase partition column chromatography as a method of analysis. The study of the oil by gas chromatographic method has not been reported so far.

Experimental

Authentic samples of the oil seeds used in the present investigation were obtained through the kind courtesy of the Silviculturist, Maharashtra State. *Mesua ferrea* seeds however, were obtained through the Silviculturist, Mysore State.

The seeds were broken by suitable methods and the shells were separated from the kernels. The kernels were powdered and moisture content was determined. In the case of *Michelia champaca* however, the seeds were crushed along with the shells. The oil content was determined in a continuous soxhlet extractor using commercial hexane (B.P. 66-69) as solvent. The characteristics of the oils were determined by conventional methods. The results are presented in Table 1.

The mixed fatty acids of the oils freed from unsaponifiable matter were converted into their methyl esters by refluxing for one hour with methanol containing 1% sulphuric acid. The esters were freed from mineral acid and were analysed for their individual fatty acid components by an F & M Model 720 dual column Gas chromatograph equipped with thermal conductivity detector and Honeywell Brown recorder. The column, 10 ft long and 4 mm inner diameter,

was packed with 20 per cent diethylene glycol succinate on Chromosorb W (80-100 mesh). The temperature of the column was 200°C and that of the detector was 280°C. Hydrogen was used as a carrier gas with a flow of 60 ml per min. The speed of the chart was 15 in per hr.

Comparison of the retention times of the fatty acid methyl esters of the oils with the retention times of pure fatty acid methyl esters analysed under identical conditions aided in the direct identification of the peaks on the chromatographic record. Identification of saturated and unsaturated methyl esters was further confirmed by plotting the log of retention times versus the number of carbon atoms in the chain²⁷. The peak areas were calculated by the method of triangulation²⁸. The data calculated as wt. per cent of fatty acids is given in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

Bombax malabaricum oil (38.3% on kernel) is yellow in colour. The characteristics of the oil compared well with the values reported by Kinzo Kafuku² and Venkata Rao *et al.*³

The major fatty acid components of the oil are palmitic acid (38.6%) and linoleic acid (34.0%). The palmitic acid content of the oil is found to be a little higher than the value reported by Kinzo Kafuku² (28.3%). The present data also shows less of oleic acid (17.0%) and more of linoleic acid contents as compared to the reported values wherein oleic acid is major and linoleic acid is minor. Further, myristic acid is found to be less than 0.1% and behenic and lignoceric acids are present to the extent of 1.7% and 2.9% respectively.

Buchanania lanzan: The kernel gave 51.5% of pale yellow oil. The only available report on the characteristics and fatty acid composition of this oil is that by Godbole *et al.*⁵ The iodine value (56.3), minimum amongst the samples analysed, somewhat agrees with the reported value (62.4)⁵. The other characteristics of the oil are also comparable with the reported values.

The major components of the oil are palmitic (34.1%) and oleic (55.2%). The other components are myristic (0.1%), hexadecenoic (1.7%), stearic acid (7.3%) and linoleic acid (4.6%). The present data agrees very well with the data reported by Godbole *et al.*⁵ However, the presence of hexadecenoic acid could not be detected by earlier workers.

Mesua ferrea seeds were found to have maximum oil content (76.7% on kernel) and compared well with the reported values (60% and 70%). The oil has red colour and slight disagreeable odour.

The characteristics of the oil compare well with the reported values except iodine value (74.5) which is somewhat lower than the reported value (81.1-92.7). However, the present iodine value compares very well with the iodine value reported by Badami *et al.*¹²

The oil consists mainly of C₁₈ acids (81.0%) out of which oleic acid content is as high as 59.9%. The other acids present are myristic (0.1%), palmitic

TABLE 1. CHARACTERISTICS OF OILSEEDS AND OILS

Botanical Name	Common Name	Characteristics of seeds		Characteristics of the oils							
		Moisture %	Oil % (Wet basis)	Colour	Refractive index 30°C	Specific gravity 30°C	S.V.	I.V.	A.V.	UM%	Consistency
1. <i>Bombax malabaricum</i>	Savar	6.4	38.3	20y+1.3R	1.4641	0.9024	199.5	73.4	10.6	1.23	Liquid
2. <i>Buchanania lanzan</i>	Charoly	5.8	51.5	2.5y+0.6R	1.4622	0.9246	203.5	56.3	13.5	1.11	Liquid
3. <i>Mesua ferrea</i>	Nahor	3.4	76.7	13y+17R	1.4688	0.9263	200.2	74.5	7.4	2.82	Liquid
4. <i>Michelia champaca</i>	Champha	7.6	25.1	30y+14R+4B	1.4669	0.9142	204.8	88.3	8.7	3.11	Liquid
5. <i>Terminalia catappa</i>	Jangli badam	10.2	55.5	10y+0.5R	1.4618	0.9032	204.8	71.4	1.9	0.62	Liquid
6. <i>Thespesia populnea</i>	Bhendi	10.5	34.0	30y+8.3R	1.4596	0.9246	201.3	99.3	3.3	1.20	Liquid
7. <i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	Gokhru	9.3	34.8	5.1y+0.6R	1.4685	0.9041	194.5	135.5	1.1	1.10	Liquid

TABLE 2. FATTY ACID COMPOSITION OF THE OILS

Species	Ref.	14:0	16:0	16:1	18:0	18:1	18:2	20:0	22:0	24:0
1. <i>Bombax malabaricum</i>	2	—	28.3	—	7.3	49.9	14.5	—	—	—
	3	1.2	23.6	—	—	64.9	7.5	2.6	—	—
	++	<0.1	38.6	—	4.0	17.0	34.0	1.8	1.7	2.9
2. <i>Buchanania lanzan</i>	5	0.1	28.9	—	8.1	57.4	5.5	—	—	—
	++	0.1	34.1	1.7	7.3	55.2	4.6	—	—	—
	9	0.2	12.5	—	13.5	59.8	14.0	—	—	—
3. <i>Mesua ferrea</i>	10	—	4.9	—	9.2	65.4	20.5	—	—	—
	11*	0.1	16.3	0.3	15.2	57.4	6.4	0.8	0.2	<0.1
	12	0.9	19.5	—	10.8	44.5	19.2	2.6	2.5	—
	++	0.1	17.4	1.5	12.1	59.9	9.0	—	—	—
	14	—	30.0	—	—	70.0	—	—	—	—
4. <i>Michelia champaca</i>	15†	0.4	20.7	6.9	2.5	22.3	42.5	2.6	—	—
	++	1.1	36.4	1.9	6.2	15.9	38.5	—	—	—
	20	1.0	28.5	—	4.0	40.8	22.9	0.7	—	—
5. <i>Terminalia catappa</i>	21	0.7	36.5	—	3.8	35.1	17.9	—	—	—
	17	1.6	55.5	—	6.3	23.3	7.6	—	—	—
	++	—	38.7	—	3.1	40.0	18.2	—	—	—
	24	1.0	21.4	—	1.9	32.5	43.2	—	—	—
6. <i>Thespesia populnea</i>	++	—	33.8	—	3.2	13.6	49.4	—	—	—
	28	satd.	11.1.....	36.7	52.2	—	—	—
	12**	0.5	8.0	—	4.0	17.3	64.8	2.0	2.3	—
7. <i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	++	—	8.3	—	3.6	16.2	69.2	—	2.7	—

* Also presence of 8:0, 1.0%; 10:0, <0.1%; 12:0, 0.1%; 14:1, 0.1%; 15:0, 0.1%; 15:1, 1.0%; 18:3, <0.1%, 20:1, <0.1% has been reported.

† 20:1, 0.8% has been reported.

** 8:0, 0.6%; 10:0, 0.3% and 12:0, 0.2% have also been reported.

++ Present work.

(17.4%), hexadecenoic (1.5%), stearic (12.1%) and linoleic (9.0%). In respect of these components, the present data is in close agreement with the GLC data reported by Sreenivasan¹¹. However, other minor acids reported by him were found to be absent. The present data also compares with the fractionation data reported by Kasturi *et al.*⁹ even as far as minor components are concerned.

Michelia champaca: The seed has minimum oil content (25.5%) among the seeds analysed perhaps because the oil content is based on seed basis and not on kernel basis. The oil has dark reddish brown colour and pleasant odour. The saponification value (204.8) is higher than that reported by Bedi *et al.*¹⁴ but is somewhat nearer to that of Sack¹³ (196-199).

The iodine value 88.3 is lower than that reported by Bedi *et al.*¹⁴ (104.7) and higher than the value reported by Sack¹³ (60.3). The rest of the characteristics compare well with the results obtained by Bedi *et al.*¹⁴ This oil has the maximum unsaponifiable matter (3.1%) among the oils analysed.

The major components of the oil are palmitic (36.4%) and linoleic (38.5%) which compare well with the values reported by Badami *et al.*¹² (palmitic 31.8% and linoleic 34.7%). The other acids present are myristic (1.1%), hexadecenoic (1.9%), stearic (6.2%) and oleic (15.9%). However, arachidic and eicosenoic acids reported by Bedi *et al.*¹⁴ are found to be absent.

Terminalia catappa oil (55.5% on kernels) had low acid value (1.9) and low unsaponifiable matter (0.62%). The characteristics of the oil compare well with the reported values.

The major fatty acid components of the oil are palmitic (38.7%) and oleic (40.0%). The other components present are stearic (3.1%) and linoleic (18.2%). The present data is in agreement with the data reported by Asenjo *et al.*¹⁷ except that myristic acid was found to be absent.

Thespesia populnea gave 34% of oil having reddish brown colour. The characteristics of the oil (SV 201.3, AV 3.3, unsap. 1.2%) are near to the only available literature values²³ (SV 203.2, AV 0.5, unsap. 0.72%). However, the present iodine value (99.3) is higher than the reported value²³ (71.5).

The oil has palmitic (33.8%) and linoleic (49.4%) as major fatty acids and these values are somewhat comparable with the values reported by Subbaram²³. The other acids present are stearic 3.2% and oleic 13.6%. The oleic acid content of the present oil is found to be lower than the reported value²³ (32.5%).

Xanthium strumarium seed kernel contains 34.8% of yellow coloured oil and is found to have minimum acid value (1.1) and maximum iodine value (135.5) among the samples analysed. The characteristics of the oil (SV 194.5, IV 135.5, AV 1.1 and unsap. matter 1.1%) compare well with the values reported by Branke *et al.*²⁴ (SV 189.8, IV 137.4, AV 0.66 and unsap. matter 0.85%).

The oil consists mainly of C₁₈ acids to the extent of (89.0%) and is very unsaturated. Among the unsaturated acids linoleic acid content is as high as 69.2%, the highest among the oils studied in the present investigation. The present data compares very well with the reversed phase partition column chromatographic data reported by Badami *et al.*¹² except that C₈, C₁₀, C₁₂ and C₂₀ are found to be absent in the present investigation.

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